

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Kazutaka Yoshida

Email: Kazutaka_Yoshida@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: April 18, 2025 Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on vascular endothelial function

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

医中誌 Web

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

医中誌 Web

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).
- I** Oral intake of lycopene
- C** Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention
- O** Vascular endothelial function assessed by flow-mediated dilation (FMD), reactive hyperemia peripheral arterial tonometry (RH-PAT), or plethysmograph
- S** Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

- #1 Lycopene/TH or リコピン/AL or Lycopene/AL or リコペン/AL or ϕ -カロテン/AL or プサイカロテン/AL or psi
カロテン/AL or ϕ -Carotene/AL or psi-Carotene/AL or LYC-O-MATO/AL or LYCOMATO/AL or "LYC O MATO"/AL or
ATERONON/AL or "BLAKESLEA TRISPORA"/AL or "CI 75125"/AL or CI-75125/AL or CI75125/AL or "E 160D"/AL or E-
160D/AL or E160D/AL or LYCORED/AL or "MEXORYL SAQ"/AL or MEXORYL-SAQ/AL or "NSC 407322"/AL or NSC-
407322/AL or NSC407322/AL or REDIVIVO/AL or SOLANORUBIN/AL or "TOMAT O RED"/AL or TOMAT-O-RED/AL or
502-65-8/AL or 13018-46-7/AL or トマト/TH or トマト/TA or "Lycopersicon esculentum"/AL or "Solanum
lycopersicum"/AL or Tomato/TA or 赤茄子/AL or アカナス/AL or あかなす/AL or 蕃茄/AL or 唐柿/AL or 小金瓜/AL or コ
ガネウリ/AL or 珊瑚樹茄子/AL or さんごじゅなす/AL or サンゴジュナス/AL or スイカ属/TH or スイカ/TA or Citrullus/AL
or "Water Melon"/TA or Watermelon/TA or 西瓜/AL 2,347
- #2 血管内皮/TH or 血管内皮/AL or "vascular endotheli"/AL or "vessel endotheli"/AL or 脈管内皮/AL or 脈内皮/AL or
内皮機能/AL or "Capillary Endotheli"/AL or "endothel funct"/AL or "endothel dysfunct"/AL or (血管/TH or 内皮/TH or 血管
/AL or 脈管/AL or 脈内/AL or Blood/AL or Vessel/AL or Vascul/AL or Vein/AL or Endothel/AL) ?
- #3 FMD/AL or "Flow-mediated Dilation"/AL or "Flow mediated Dilation"/AL or "Flow-mediated Vasodilation"/AL or
"Flow mediated Vasodilation"/AL or "血流依存性血管拡張反応"/AL or "内皮依存性血管拡張反応"/AL 1,777
- #4 RH-PAT/AL or RHPAT/AL or "reactive hyperemia peripheral arterial tonometry"/AL or "Reactive Hyperemia-
Peripheral Arterial Tonometry"/AL or 反応性充血末梢動脈トノメトリー/AL or 反応性充血末梢動脈圧力測定/AL or 末梢
動脈トノメトリー/AL or 末梢動脈圧力測定/AL 115
- #5 プレチスモグラフィ/TH or Plethysmograph/AL or プレスチモグラフ/AL or プレチスモグラフ/AL or プレシス
モグラフ/AL or 容積脈波/AL or 体積記録/AL or 体積変動記録/AL 4,571
- #6 #2 or #3 or #4 or #5 1,233,719
- #7 #1 and #6 and PT=原著論文,総説 105
- #8 (#7 and CK=ヒト) or (#7 not (CK=イヌ,ネコ,ウシ,ウマ,ブタ,ヒツジ,サル,ウサギ,ニワトリ,鶏胚,モルモット,ハム
スター,マウス,ラット,カエル,動物)) 88
- #9 #8 not (トマトレクチン/AL or セルオートマトン/AL or ヒトマトリックス/AL or ヒトマトリクス/AL or ニットマ
トリックス/AL or エリトマトーデス/AL or tomatous/AL or tomatosis/AL or tdTomato/AL or スイカ胃/AL or スイカ状/AL
or スイカ縞/AL or "Watermelon stomach"/AL or "watermelon type"/AL or watermelon 型/AL or Symptomatology/AL or
Stomatocytology/AL or スイカズラ/AL) 18

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: April 30, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

#8・・・ヒト対象研究に絞る場合、一般的には、「○○ not (動物 not ヒト)」のような消去方法を用いる方がより除外されすぎないかと思えます。ヒトと動物の両方のチェックタグ (CK) が振られている文献もあるためです。

ただ、今回#7→#8 で除外された 17 件にはヒト対象研究が含まれていないので、今回に限ってはこの#8 のままでも支障はないのですが。

#9・・・この件数までノイズを除外する必要性があればこのように NOT 検索を行ってもよいかと思えますが、適格論文で偶然にこれらのキーワードを抄録内に含むような文献も NOT すると除外されてしまうため、NOT 検索はあまりおすすめしません。

※#7 を最終式としてもよいかと考えますが、いかがでしょうか。方針に合わせてご検討ください。

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Kazutaka Yoshida

Email: Kazutaka_Yoshida@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: March 27, 2025 Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on vascular endothelial function

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

MEDLINE

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

PubMed

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).
- I** Oral intake of lycopene
- C** Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention
- O** Vascular endothelial function assessed by flow-mediated dilation (FMD), reactive hyperemia peripheral arterial tonometry (RH-PAT), or plethysmograph
- S** Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 "lycopene"[Supplementary Concept] OR "lycopene"[MeSH Terms] OR "lycopene**"[All Fields] 7,063
#2 "solanum lycopersicum"[MeSH Terms] OR "lycopersicon esculentum"[All Fields] OR "tomato**"[All Fields] OR
"watermelon**"[All Fields] OR "water melon**"[All Fields] 41,111
#3 #1 OR #2 46,123
#4 "randomized controlled trial"[Publication Type] OR "controlled clinical trial"[Publication Type] OR
"randomized"[Title/Abstract] OR "placebo"[Title/Abstract] OR "clinical trials as topic"[MeSH Terms:noexp] OR
"randomly"[Title/Abstract] OR "trial"[Title] 1,686,152
#5 "case control studies"[MeSH Terms] OR "control groups"[MeSH Terms] OR ("case**"[Title/Abstract] AND
"control**"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("case**"[Title/Abstract] AND "comparison**"[Title/Abstract]) OR "control
group**"[Title/Abstract] OR "cohort studies"[MeSH Terms] OR "cohort"[Title/Abstract] OR "longitudinal"[Title/Abstract]
OR "prospective"[Title/Abstract] OR "retrospective"[Title/Abstract] OR "cross sectional studies"[MeSH Terms] OR
"cross-sectional"[Title/Abstract] OR "transversal stud**"[Title/Abstract] 5,417,610
#6 #4 OR #5 6,502,235
#7 #6 NOT ("animals"[MeSH Terms] NOT "humans"[MeSH Terms]) 6,150,160
#8 #3 AND #7 3,281
#9 "vascular "[Title/Abstract] OR "endothelial"[Title/Abstract] OR "blood vessels"[All Fields] OR "blood vessels"[MeSH
Terms] OR "flow mediated dilatation"[All Fields] OR "plethysmograph "[All Fields] OR "RH-PAT"[All Fields] OR
"peripheral arterial tonometry" [All Fields] 1,529,085
#10 #8 AND #9 171

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: April 11, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

“endothelial”[Title/Abstract]は、endotheli*[Title/Abstract]としてもよいかと思ひます。
(endothelial, endothelium の両方を拾えるため)
“blood vessels”[All Fields]は、 “blood vessel*”[All Fields] としてもよいかと思ひます。

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Kazutaka Yoshida

Email: Kazutaka_Yoshida@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: April 15, 2025 Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on vascular endothelial function

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library/Wiley

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).
- I** Oral intake of lycopene
- C** Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention
- O** Vascular endothelial function assessed by flow-mediated dilation (FMD), reactive hyperemia peripheral arterial tonometry (RH-PAT), or plethysmograph
- S** Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

- #1 (lycopene* OR Prolycopene OR Pro-Lycopene OR Pro Lycopene OR LYC-O-MATO OR LYCOMATO OR LYC O MATO OR All-trans-Lycopene):ti,ab,kw 757
- #2 MeSH descriptor: [Lycopene] explode all trees 305
- #3 MeSH descriptor: [Solanum lycopersicum] explode all trees 143
- #4 (tomato OR tomatoes OR solanum lycopersicum OR lycopersicon esculentum OR watermelon OR water melon):ti,ab,kw 829
- #5 #1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 1,345
- #6 MeSH descriptor: [Blood Vessels] explode all trees 18,366
- #7 (vascular OR endotheli* OR blood vessel* OR flow mediated dilatation OR plethysmograph OR RH-PAT OR peripheral arterial tonometry):ti,ab,kw 76,188
- #8 #6 OR #7 84,813
- #9 #5 AND #8 in Trials 114

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: April 30, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

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5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

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Acknowledgement

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- This is my first submission
- This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).
- I** Oral intake of lycopene
- C** Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention
- O** Vascular endothelial function assessed by flow-mediated dilation (FMD), reactive hyperemia peripheral arterial tonometry (RH-PAT), or plethysmograph
- S** Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 ((lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") OR (mh:"lycopene")) AND (((random* OR trial* OR placebo OR cohort OR case-control* OR cross-section*)) OR (mh:("Clinical Study" OR "Clinical Trial" OR "Randomized Controlled Trial" OR "Controlled Clinical Trial" OR "Epidemiologic Studies" OR "Case-Control Studies" OR "Cohort Studies" OR "Cross-Sectional Studies")))) 93

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: April 30, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Kazutaka Yoshida

Email: Kazutaka_Yoshida@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: April 15, 2025 Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on vascular endothelial function

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).
- I** Oral intake of lycopene
- C** Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention
- O** Vascular endothelial function assessed by flow-mediated dilation (FMD), reactive hyperemia peripheral arterial tonometry (RH-PAT), or plethysmograph
- S** Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 (lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in the Title :Recruitment status is ALL 110 records for 108 trials

#2 (lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in the Intervention :Recruitment status is ALL 137 records for 135 trials

#3 #1 OR #2 137 records for 135 trials

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: April 30, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).
- I** Oral intake of lycopene
- C** Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention
- O** Vascular endothelial function assessed by flow-mediated dilation (FMD), reactive hyperemia peripheral arterial tonometry (RH-PAT), or plethysmograph
- S** Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 (lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in Other terms 119

#2 (lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in Intervention/treatmen 84

#3 #1 OR #2 119

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: April 30, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

送っていただいた#3 が、以下のリンク（式）でマージされることを確認しました。

[https://clinicaltrials.gov/expert-search?term=AREA%5BInterventionSearch%5D\(\(lycopene*%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20\(13-cis\)-isomer%22%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20\(7-cis,%207%27-cis,%209-cis,%209%27-cis\)-isomer%20-%22%20R%20%22Prolycopene%22%20R%20%22Pro-Lycopene%22%20R%20%22Pro%20Lycopene%22%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20\(cis\)-isomer%22%20R%20%22LYC-OMATO%22%20R%20%22LYCOMATO%22%20R%20%22LYC%20O%20MATO%22%20R%20%22All-trans-Lycopene%22%20R%20%22All%20trans%20Lycopene%22\)\)%20R%20AREA%5BBasicSearch%5D\(\(lycopene*%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20\(13-cis\)-isomer%22%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20\(7-cis,%207%27-cis,%209-cis,%209%27-cis\)-isomer%20-%22%20R%20%22Prolycopene%22%20R%20%22Pro-Lycopene%22%20R%20%22Pro%20Lycopene%22%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20\(cis\)-isomer%22%20R%20%22LYC-OMATO%22%20R%20%22LYCOMATO%22%20R%20%22LYC%20O%20MATO%22%20R%20%22All-trans-Lycopene%22%20R%20%22All%20trans%20Lycopene%22\)\)](https://clinicaltrials.gov/expert-search?term=AREA%5BInterventionSearch%5D((lycopene*%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20(13-cis)-isomer%22%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20(7-cis,%207%27-cis,%209-cis,%209%27-cis)-isomer%20-%22%20R%20%22Prolycopene%22%20R%20%22Pro-Lycopene%22%20R%20%22Pro%20Lycopene%22%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20(cis)-isomer%22%20R%20%22LYC-OMATO%22%20R%20%22LYCOMATO%22%20R%20%22LYC%20O%20MATO%22%20R%20%22All-trans-Lycopene%22%20R%20%22All%20trans%20Lycopene%22))%20R%20AREA%5BBasicSearch%5D((lycopene*%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20(13-cis)-isomer%22%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20(7-cis,%207%27-cis,%209-cis,%209%27-cis)-isomer%20-%22%20R%20%22Prolycopene%22%20R%20%22Pro-Lycopene%22%20R%20%22Pro%20Lycopene%22%20R%20%22Lycopene,%20(cis)-isomer%22%20R%20%22LYC-OMATO%22%20R%20%22LYCOMATO%22%20R%20%22LYC%20O%20MATO%22%20R%20%22All-trans-Lycopene%22%20R%20%22All%20trans%20Lycopene%22)))

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

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Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Kazutaka Yoshida

Email: Kazutaka_Yoshida@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: April 15, 2025 Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on vascular endothelial function

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission
- This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission
- This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

University Hospital Medical Information Network-Clinical Trials Registry (UMIN-CTR)

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

University Hospital Medical Information Network-Clinical Trials Registry (UMIN-CTR)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).
- I** Oral intake of lycopene
- C** Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention
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- S** Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1	リコピン	20	
#2	リコペン	8	
#3	プロリコピン	0	
#4	ライコマート	0	
#5	lycopene	25	
#6	prolycopene	0	
#7	LYC-O-MATO	0	
#8	All-trans-lycopene	0	
#9	#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8	29	

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: April 30, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>